

University of Warsaw
Faculty of "Artes Liberales"
Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA)
and the Cluster The Past for the Present

International Conference, Online

SEPTEMBER 29–30, 2021

ERC Consolidator Grant (681202)

Our Mythical Childhood...
The Reception of Classical Antiquity
in Children's and Young Adults' Culture
in Response to Regional and Global Challenges

Lectures and presentations: <http://omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/our-mythical-nature>

We begin at: 9 p.m. CEST (Bologna-Fribourg-Munich-Vienna-Warsaw)

Time Zones: 8 p.m. (London-Yaoundé); 10 p.m. (Tel-Aviv); 3 p.m. (New York-Pennsylvania);
5 a.m. + one day (Sydney); 8 a.m. + one day (Palmerston North)

SEPTEMBER 29, 2021 (WEDNESDAY)

Introductory remarks 5 minutes

PANEL 1 *Our Mythical Nature across the World*, 30 minutes, moderated by Amy Smith, Ure Museum, University of Reading

- Helen Lovatt, Department of Classics and Archaeology, University of Nottingham, *Bernard Evslin and the Clashing Rocks*
- Sonya Nevin, School of Humanities, University of Roehampton / Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Imagining Africa: Classical Antiquity in the Brontë Juvenilia*
- Daniel A. Nkemele, Divine Che Neba, Eleanor A. Dasi, Department of English ENS, University of Yaoundé 1, *Nature Dynamics: From Descriptive to Prescriptive Nature Images in Yael Farber's "Molara"*
- Elizabeth Hale, School of Arts, University of New England, *Witi Ihimaera's "Whale Rider" and the Ulysses of the Pacific*
- Miriam Riverlea, Faculty of Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Education, University of New England, *Bushfire, Myths and Mallacoota* (Miriam is unable to attend, but we will gather feedback for her)

PANEL 2 *Animal Nature(s)*, 30 minutes, moderated by David Movrin, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Ljubljana

- Elżbieta Olechowska, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Nothing Ancient Resonates with Children as Deeply as the Concept of an Animal Dæmon. Philip Pullman's Scenario for the Human-Animal Bond*
- Ayelet Peer, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University, *Heroic Beasts: On Humans-Animals Relations in Lucy Coats' "Beasts of Olympus" Series*
- Lisa Maurice, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University, *The God Pan in Children's Fiction and Culture*
- Robin Diver, Department of Classics, Ancient History and Archaeology, University of Birmingham, *The Problem of Animals and Rape: Children's Anthology Adaptations of the God Pan*
- Amanda Potter, Open University, *Save the Monster, Save the World: Living in Harmony with 'Monsters' in "Nausicaä of the Valley of the Wind" (1984) and "Princess Mononoke" (1997)*

PANEL 3 *All of Nature's Senses*, 30 minutes, moderated by Hanna Paulouskaya, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw

- Karolina Anna Kulpa, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Antiquity Flavours in the Literary Cuisine of Małgorzata Musierowicz*
- Krzysztof Rybak, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Serving Ancient Nature in Informational Picturebooks: Natural Products and Their Consumption in Antiquity and Beyond*
- Anna Mik, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Mythical Labyrinthine Nature in Jan Bajtlik's "Greek Myths and Mazes"*
- Katerina Volioti, School of Humanities, University of Roehampton, *A Post-humanist Perspective: Plants, Animals, and Things in Children's Books about the Classical Past*
- Beatrice Palmieri, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna / Erasmus Programme, *Gianni Rodari and the Myth of Atalanta: The Role of Nature in Knowledge of Culture*

PANEL 4 *Constellations of Nature*, 25 minutes, moderated by Frances Foster, Faculty of Education, University of Cambridge

- Rachel Bryant Davies, School of Languages, Linguistics and Film, Queen Mary University of London, *"The frailty of sublunary things": Classical Myth, Pedagogical Media, and Moral Education in the Eighteenth and Nineteenth Centuries*
- Katarzyna Jerzak, Institute of Modern Languages, Pomeranian University in Słupsk, *A Dead Bird and a Cenotaph: Echoes of Antiquity in Janusz Korczak's "King Matt on the Desert Island" (1923) and Margaret Wise Brown's "The Dead Bird" (1938)*
- Hanna Paulouskaya, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Constellations of Gods in Soviet Animation*
- Krishni Burns, Department of Classics and Mediterranean Studies, University of Illinois Chicago, *Mythical Skyscapes: Constellation Myths in Educational Picture Books*

Book presentations, 10 minutes

Olympus Ready-to-Wear, 10 minutes, moderated by Andrea Balbo, Department of Humanities, University of Turin

Presentation of a game (<http://omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/ready-to-wear>) created by Alessia Borriello and Ludovica Lusvardi. Alessia is a student from the Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies at the University of Bologna and in Winter term of 2019/20 accomplished her Erasmus Plus stay at the Faculty of "Artes Liberales" at the University of Warsaw and participated in the *Our Mythical Childhood* project. Ludovica is a graduate from Fashion Design at Politecnico of Milan and continues her training at the Theatrical Tailoring at Accademia della Scala. Martina Treu, Department of Humanities, Università IULM, will contribute to the presentation by referring to her experience with the game during a workshop she organized for children in Milan in June 2021.

Conclusions 5 minutes

SEPTEMBER 30, 2021 (THURSDAY)

Introductory remarks 5 minutes

PANEL 5 *Myth and Nature of the Past*, 30 minutes, moderated by Berkan Sariaydin, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich

- Raimund Fichtel, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, *The Venus Grotto of Ludwig II of Bavaria – The Childhood Dream of a Gentle Tiberius*
- Sonja Schreiner, Department of Classical Philology, Medieval and Neolatin Studies, University of Vienna, *Witty Education: Environment and Nature as Atmospheric Background in Friedrich Wilhelm Zachariä's (1726–1777) Mock Heroic Poetry*
- Christian Laes, School of Arts, Languages and Cultures, University of Manchester, *Antiquity's Childhood and Toys in Alfredo Bartoli's "Filius ad Matrem Reversus" (1950)*
- Jan Kieniewicz, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Mytho-picture: Combining Myth and Nature in the Patriotic Landscape*
- Edith Hall, Department of Classics, King's College London, *Muscular Christian Classicism: Nature, Race and (Anti-)Science in Charles Kingsley's "The Water Babies"*

PANEL 6 *The Nature of Hero(ine)s – the Hero(ine)s of Nature*, 30 minutes, moderated by Anastasia Bakogianni, Classical Studies, Massey University

- Susan Deacy, School of Humanities, University of Roehampton, *"Hercules [...] went out to a quiet place and sat, pondering" (Xenophon, "Memorabilia" 2.1.21): What Happened Here and Why It "Speaks" to Autistic Children*
- Edoardo Pecchini, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Promoting Mental Health through Classics: Odysseus*
- Robert A. Sucharski, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Halina Rudnicka and Her Ancient Trilogy or on the Nature of the True Hero(ine)s*
- Sheila Murnaghan, Department of Classical Studies, University of Pennsylvania, *The Secret Lives of Trees: Tales of Natural Transformation in Classical Myths for Children*
- Markus Janka, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, *"Mens antiqua manet" – "The Mind of Old Remains" (Ovid, "Metamorphoses" 2.485): Humanized Animals in Ovid's "Metamorphoses" and Contemporary Children's and Young Adults' Literature*

PANEL 7 *Under the Auspices of Animals*, 30 minutes, moderated by Mark O'Connor, Arts & Sciences Honors Program, Boston College

- Véronique Dasen, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg/ERC Locus Ludi, *From Greek Amulets to Contemporary Jewellery: The Secret Agency of Nature and Animals in the Life Cycle of Young Individuals*
- Jerzy Axer, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Reading from Genesis (3:1–24) for Animals*
- Nick Lowe, Department of Classics, Royal Holloway, University of London, *What is it Like to be an Elephant?*
- Owen Hodgkinson, Faculty of Arts, Humanities and Cultures, University of Leeds, *Shaggy Dog Stories: Two Novels of Odysseus' Dog Argos*
- Marta Pszczolińska, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Domestic Animals: Minimus the Mouse and Vibrissa the Cat as a Latin Learning Supporting Team in "Minimus. Starting out in Latin" Textbook*

PANEL 8 *Hope after Disaster*, 30 minutes, moderated by Valentina Garulli, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna

- Deborah H. Roberts, Department of Classics, Haverford College, *Natural Disaster, Social Change: Volcanic Eruptions in Children's Literature and the Story of Thera*
- Babette Puetz, School of Languages and Cultures, Victoria University of Wellington, *"No matter how dark the night, the sun always rises": The AD 79 Vesuvius Eruption in Contemporary Children's Literature*
- Przemysław Kordos, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Low Fantasy, High Conscience: Ecology in Some Exomimetic Worlds*
- Michael Stierstorfer, Gymnasium Kloster Schäfflarn, *The Reception of Atlantis in Current Children's Media as an (Un-)Natural Island*
- Katarzyna Marciniak, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Geralt on Climate Strikes: Ancient Motifs and Ecology in Andrzej Sapkowski's Short-Stories of the Witcher Cycle*

Sappho Sings, 10 minutes

- Caroline Bristow, Cambridge School Classics Project, University of Cambridge, and Sonya Nevin, School of Humanities, University of Roehampton / Panoply Vase Animation Project, *A Good Night (or Day) Song from the Past for the Present*

Steve K. Simons' Mythical Surprise, 10 minutes

- Only Steve, School of Humanities, University of Roehampton / Panoply Vase Animation Project, knows the content of this point.

Conclusions 5 minutes

This Project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 681202, *Our Mythical Childhood... The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges*, ERC Consolidator Grant (2016–2021).